

PROFESSIONAL READINESS OF FUTURE TEACHERS TO WORK IN THE INCLUSIVE EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract. *The humanistic goal of teacher education integrates the personal position of the future teacher (motivational and value-based attitude towards teaching activity) and his professional knowledge, abilities, and skills (professional competence). This unity determines the level of development of a teacher or educator working with children with disabilities as a humanist teacher, which ensures his readiness to take responsibility for the fate of a child with developmental disabilities, for his future.*

Keywords: *children with special educational needs; tolerance; psychological training; internal motivation; teacher.*

Introduction. Inclusive education is a process of collaborative education and upbringing of people with special educational needs and normally developing children. In the process of inclusive education, students with disabilities have the opportunity to achieve great success in social and psychological development. Inclusive education is a form of education in which students with special educational needs: go to school with their brothers, sisters, and neighbours; study in classes with their peers; have individual learning goals that fit their abilities and needs; receive the support they need. Inclusive education requires special psychological and pedagogical readiness, not only specially created comfortable conditions for children with disabilities [1-3].

One of the purposes of inclusive education is to create a psychologically pleasant educational environment for children with disabilities in the process of educational communication. The socialisation of children with disabilities among children without developmental disabilities is ensured through their interaction, mutual assistance, and support. From an early age, a child with special physical needs has the opportunity to overcome difficulties, live in real conditions, and feel like a complete part of society [4; 5].

Currently, the transformation of the content of vocational pedagogical education has the following components:

cognitive: students' mastery of professional knowledge, which is realized through perception, understanding, assimilation of material and their use in various pedagogical situations;

activity-based: expressed in the ability to possess practical knowledge and skills for the implementation of professional activities in various pedagogical situations;

experience in creative pedagogical activity: aimed at the process of comprehending professional activity through partial search and research activities, the ability to find a pedagogical problem and ways to solve it;

experience of value-emotional orientation: this is a process of professional pedagogical activity that contains three stages: the formation of the teacher's internal motivation, professional pedagogical behavior, and the creative focus of pedagogical activity [5].

The motivational and value component of the future teacher's readiness for professional activity includes: attitude towards the profession; the predominance of motives for communication with society; desire for self-realization in the teaching profession; the desire to constantly improve in it.

The cognitive-evaluative component covers the awareness of students - future teachers - about the essence and meaning of their chosen profession, about the requirements for the content of the personality of a specialist in this profile, as well as the level of competencies necessary for professional teaching activities.

The personal component implies the degree of moral and psychological readiness of the student for professional teaching activity. It reflects the degree of formation of authoritative value orientations, interest in the chosen profession, satisfaction with its results, the level of development of professional training and participation in self-improvement activities.

The emotional-volitional component of readiness reflects self-control, moral principles, a sense of responsibility for the results of activities, the ability to manage the actions that make up the performance of functional duties, the degree of practical readiness of the future specialist in the field of professional activity [2].

Based on an analysis of the literature, by professional readiness we understand a complex phenomenon implemented on the basis of a personal approach to the process of preparing students for teaching professional activities, which characterizes the presence of qualities necessary for future work, the ability to clearly and immediately make decisions, demonstrate interest in their profession, be able to maintain contact with students, master the techniques of pedagogical interaction

We consider readiness as a systemic process of personality formation for inclusive pedagogical practice, which has the following personal characteristics:

- the ability to organize teaching activities in a collaborative environment;
- the ability to consciously choose options for one's own professional behavior;
- the ability to easily navigate the system of techniques and methods of pedagogical activity;
- willingness and ability to choose adequate means and methods of self-development [7].

For successful teaching activities in the structure of teacher education, conventional pedagogical training is completely insufficient. The future teacher must develop his reflective skills and replenish his arsenal of pedagogical techniques, be able to analyze style, techniques, teaching methods, and learn to effectively build interaction.

The main function in the professional readiness of students is moral education. Sustainable moral behavior and moral feelings that correspond to the modern way of life of a real teacher, to form in their actions and actions the active life position of each person towards feelings of social duty.

An axiological approach to the formation of professional readiness of a modern teacher means that the knowledge, abilities, skills acquired by a student during his studies at a university (and then by a teacher in the process of continuous self-education) only then develop into

competence (that is, they acquire the character of sustainable ways of personal activity) when they have a positive value connotation in his professional activities.

In order to become a specialist capable of working with children with disabilities, he needs to know not only pedagogy and psychology, but also the sociocultural field. The efficiency and quality of work of a higher educational institution are determined primarily by how realistically the graduate meets the requirements of the State Standard of Professional Training. Issues related to the formation of the professional readiness of a novice teacher and the professional and pedagogical orientation of all his training are given a lot of attention in modern scientific research.

Thus, the professional and personal readiness of a teacher to work in the inclusive education system presupposes the formation of a whole complex of specific qualities, the improvement of which will contribute to:

introducing students to the world of ideas about children with disabilities along with NSD, deepening knowledge about the specifics of teaching children in the inclusive education system. It is important to teach future specialists ethical standards of behavior with children with disabilities;

mastering not only theoretical knowledge about morality, but also at the same time equipping students with techniques and methods of moral self-regulation, self-government and self-development in preparing children with disabilities for socialization in society.

Professional competence.

The humanistic goal of teacher education integrates the personal position of the future teacher (motivational and value-based attitude towards teaching activity) and his professional knowledge, abilities, and skills (professional competence). This unity determines the level of development of a teacher or educator working with children with disabilities as a humanist teacher, which ensures his readiness to take responsibility for the fate of a child with developmental disabilities, for his future.

As was established above, the teacher's ability to implement the humanistic function of inclusive education is associated with the professional and humanistic orientation of the individual. The formation of this focus is currently taking one of the first places in the system of university training.

The humanization of professional training of future teachers in the conditions of inclusive education is understood as the continuous general and professional development of the individuality and personality of the future employee of educational institutions. Issues of professional culture, morality, and motivation become priority issues.

Among the direct knowledge there should be knowledge saturated with humanistic content, a set of generalized knowledge about a person, the problems of his socialization if he has one or another deviation in mental, mental or physical development, relevant programs, benefits. Study of periodical literature.

Among the direct skills that a teacher working in conditions of inclusion should have are: dialogue skills, gnostic skills, didactic skills, gaming skills, organizational skills, communicative-directorial, predictive and reflective skills. Motivational skills must also be developed, i.e. be able to structure the educational process in such a way that children understand what and why they are studying and how it will be useful to them.

To complete the image of a modern teacher, it is necessary to take into account, in addition to everything previously listed, the culture of appearance. He should be an example to follow. But not in the style of clothing, of course, but in the ability to dress cleanly, neatly and comfortably. Clothes should not be “screaming”, not too bright colors, this also applies to cosmetics. The entire appearance of the teacher should not distract children from the learning process. As for the teacher’s speech itself, it must correspond to the moment. If this is a reading, a story, then it can be bright, emotional, capable of evoking a response in the child’s soul and interest him. If this is the explanation, the speech should be calm, unhurried, suggestive. The general rule for all aspects is grammatical and lexical literacy of speech, the inadmissibility of “lispings”, otherwise correct language skills will not be formed. It is also necessary to take into account the child’s deviation and adjust your speech accordingly. During communication, the teacher must show maximum tact and patience; manifestations of rudeness and hostility are completely unacceptable. Communication should be extremely polite, the mood in speech should be optimistic.

Conclusion. Analysis of the concepts of readiness for teaching activities with children in inclusive education allowed us to draw the following conclusions.

Statistical data indicate a low level of knowledge of mass school teachers in the field of special pedagogy. Today, only every fourth teacher of a comprehensive school is familiar with the basic

principles of inclusive education. Educators recognize the lack of knowledge in this area. They do not know the forms, methods and techniques of teaching and raising children with developmental disorders. This ignorance leads to the fact that

Teachers are forced to teach such children by trial and error, choosing tools and methods of work at random. Sometimes this choice may be incorrect, which negatively affects the learning process of students with disabilities and become a prerequisite for the teacher’s reluctance to work this way. On this basis, the teacher develops a negative attitude towards inclusive education in principle [14, p. 113]

For a modern teacher, inclusion is content-constructive barriers that require the formation of certain competencies to overcome them. Currently, the problem of studying and optimizing professional and personal readiness of teachers, increasing professional and pedagogical competence, mobility of a teacher working in the context of the introduction of inclusive education [10, p. 145].

Thus, in the Russian educational space, inclusive education of children with disabilities is not yet fully accepted and shared. The main reason for this is the low level of professional and personal readiness of teachers. This problem can be solved through additional training of teachers and obtaining

experience of interaction with children with various types of disabilities [24, p. 114].

Researchers note the need to train competent teachers who have a value-based attitude towards inclusion, who are able to solve professional problems in the field of teaching and providing correctional assistance to a child with disabilities and who are able to reflexively evaluate teaching activities, taking into account the negative and positive experience of inclusive practice [30, p. 37]

In inclusive education, many difficult situations arise in which most teachers prefer to seek the help of a specialist - a psychologist. Research shows that a slightly smaller proportion

would turn to the experience of colleagues. Only a small part of teachers are ready to discuss with parents the problems that arise in their relationship with their child.

Many teachers are not aware of such specialists as a speech therapist or speech pathologist. Hence the unpreparedness to interact with these

specialists carrying out the educational process. It should be noted that often teachers working in schools where there are no children with disabilities among the students do not consider the introduction of inclusion into

educational organization problem [17, p. eleven]The concept of “professional readiness” is defined differently by different researchers.

We believe that the professional readiness of university students should be considered only in connection with other personal characteristics, in which a unified pedagogical system involves creating conditions for the development of the personality of a future specialist. Acquisition of professional knowledge, skills, individual style and their implementation; practice-oriented experience of activity, reflection of professional activity - this is professional readiness, which has a certain specificity. At the same time, professional readiness itself reflects the specifics of the specific activity for which it is intended. This specificity presupposes a willingness for normally developing children and children with disabilities to work together and uniform requirements for all participants in the educational process.

Theoretical analysis of pedagogical literature has shown that the concept of “inclusive education” is ambiguous; it is understood mainly as the organization of the learning process in which all children, regardless of their physical, mental, intellectual, cultural, ethnic, linguistic and other characteristics, are included in the general education system and study locally together with their peers in the same general education organizations.

Relevant are the professional preparation of higher school students for professional activities and the development of their professional competencies in education, where there is a harmonious interaction between normally developing children and children with disabilities, as well as experience in social relations, social skills that are useful for everyone are formed, and this is sure to happen. personal self-development.

Understanding the problems of a child with disabilities as depending on a certain factor or group of factors contributes to the choice of strategy in interaction with the child and the organization of help and support for him. Also, understanding the problems that teachers face in inclusive education confronts us with the need to choose a strategy for the social and professional training of students.

In order for students of a pedagogical university to be able to work with children in the inclusive education system, they must know the characteristics of not only normally developing children, but also children with disabilities and the problems of inclusive education, and teachers of special defectology education must know the characteristics of development, methods and technologies teaching not only children with disabilities, but also normally developing children.

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